

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

A subset of the data from Cycle 2 simulations will be attributed a DOI and will be made available to the NextGEMS consortium and the wider scientific community. (Task 2.2)

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WP2

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Contents

1 Executive summary	4
2 Conclusion & Results	4
3 Project objectives	4
4 Detailed report on the deliverable	7
4.1 Cycle 2 simulations	7
4.1.1 ICON	7
4.1.2 IFS	8
4.2 Published subset of Cycle 2 model output	8
4.3 Data access via WDCC	10
5 References (Bibliography)	11
6 Dissemination and uptake	11
6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience	11
6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience	11
7 Deliverable timeliness	12
8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	12
9 Sustainability	12
9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	12
10 Full track of dissemination activities	12
11 Full track of publications and IP	13

1 Executive summary

We provide a subset of the Cycle 2 storm-resolving Earth-system simulation output freely available to the nextGEMS consortium and the wider scientific community. The subset includes a selection of frequently used 2D data fields, such as surface temperature and net radiation at top of atmosphere, at full spatial resolution (4km for IFS / 5km for ICON). The dataset is published at [WDCC](#) (World Data Center for Climate)¹, findable via the **DOI:10.26050/WDC/nextGEMS_cyc2** (Wieners et al., 2023) and accessible via [WDCC](#).

2 Conclusion & Results

A first dataset resulting out of the nextGEMS model development phase is published with an DOI attributed to it. The publication with DOI took longer than anticipated, however, with the result that we have a recipe for succeeding data publications within the project.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	

¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de>

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
<hr/> O3 <hr/>	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP2	Relevance in this deliverable?
Organizing simulation output from the pre-existing ICON and IFS DYAMOND-Winter simulations (Cycle 1 simulations) (O1)	no
To perform the Cycle 2 and initiate the Cycle 3 simulations of the Development Phase (Fig. 2) (O1)	yes
To address errors and fine-tune the SR-ESMs, including associated output and data management strategies, based on feedback from, and together with, the S&R, S&O, S&L themes (O1)	yes
To implement selected applications in SR-ESMs in collaboration with the four themes and users (O3)	no
To organise scrums to address data management and data analysis workflows in support of Hackathons and simulations analysis within NextGEMS and beyond (O1)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Within the nextGEMS project the two weather and climate models [ICON](#)² and [IFS](#)³ are developed to simulate 30 years into the future on a storm-resolving scale. The model development is split into three iterative cycles as displayed in Fig 1. In each cycle new features and improvements are implemented and thereupon tested in a simulation spanning at least one annual cycle at 5 km spatial resolution or higher. The simulations are run globally in a coupled configuration. IFS is coupled to the ocean model [FESOM](#)⁴ for the high-resolution runs at 2.8 km and 4 km, while ICON has its own ocean component ICON-O.

Figure 1: The model development in nextGEMS builds upon the work done within the [DYAMOND](#)⁵ initiative and continues in iterative cycles as shown by this graph. The rhombs denote hackathons that evaluate the main simulations towards the end of a development cycle.

4.1 Cycle 2 simulations

The focus of the present report lies on the published subset of Cycle 2 model output. To better understand the content of the published datasets we start here with a brief summary of the most recent changes to the model configurations and model physics leading up to the Cycle 2 simulations.

4.1.1 ICON

The previous *Cycle 1* configuration of ICON is thoroughly described in a recent paper by [Hohenegger et al. \(2023\)](#). For a general description of the ICON model components the reader is referred to the [ICON Wiki](#)⁶. Based on *Cycle 1*, there were several updates implemented in the development *Cycle 2*, most important:

- radiation scheme changed from psRad to [RRTMGp](#)⁷
- river discharge coupling is implemented
- new ocean spin-up with nudging to observed SST
- new ocean vertical coordinate (z^*) with thin surface levels
- bug fix of dry static energy over land

²<https://mpimet.mpg.de/en/science/models/icon-esm/>

³<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FUG/2+The+ECMWF+Integrated+Forecasting+System++IFS>

⁴<https://fesom.de/>

⁶<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/Documentation>

⁷<https://earth-system-radiation.github.io/rte-rrtmgp/>

In total, there are several model runs available, ranging from a 2-year simulation at 5 km (base run) to a 30-year simulation at 10 km horizontal resolution. Even some test runs with perturbed aerosols are available at 5 km and 10 km resolution. An overview of available datasets is provided in the [easy.gems / Cycle 2 simulation](#)⁸ chapter.

4.1.2 IFS

The *Cycle 2* IFS runs are based on the [Cycle 47r3.3](#)⁹ model configuration. In the course of the *Cycle 2* developments, the global water and energy imbalances were significantly reduced (see [nextGEMS news article](#)¹⁰). In addition, the wave model WAM is included next to several updates in the surface-atmosphere interaction:

- Multi-layer snow scheme
- Improved high-resolution land, sea, lake, and glacier masks
- Revised surface orographic drag

Updates in FESOM include:

- Refactored code allowing hybrid MPI/OpenMP support; significantly faster in the single-executable setup with IFS
- Newly developed NG5-grid with about 7.5 million surface nodes; down to 5km resolution
- New NG5 stand-alone ocean spin-up forced by ERA5 (without nudging to observed SST compared to ICON)
- Allows for linear kinematic features (sea ice cracks)
- Eddy-resolving in large areas of the globe; Tropical Instability Waves also resolved

An overview of available datasets is provided in the [easy.gems Cycle 2 simulation](#) documentation.

4.2 Published subset of Cycle 2 model output

The *Cycle 2* model runs produced in total about 1 PB of model output. A subset of the data is published at the [World Data Center for Climate \(WDCC\)](#)¹¹, a FAIR-enabling discipline-specific long-term archive focusing on the preservation of simulation-based climate science operated at DKRZ. The dataset is published including DOI provision and is further described in the following. Monthly values of selected 2d variables are saved from the main run of IFS, i.e. one full annual cycle at 4 km in the atmosphere and about 5 km horizontal resolution in the ocean (FESOM). The main run from ICON covers two simulation years performed at about 5 km horizontal resolution.

⁸<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/index.html#id1>

⁹<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/about-our-forecasts/evolution-ifs/cycles/summary-cycle-47r3>

¹⁰<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/fixing-the-water-and-energy-budget-imbalances-in-ecmwf-integrated-forecasting-systems/>

¹¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

The selected variables are:

- surface temperature at 2 m
- wind speed (ICON) and wind components (IFS) at 10 m
- precipitation
- sea surface temperature
- ocean mixed layer depth
- surface sensible and latent heat flux
- net short-wave radiation at top of atmosphere
- outgoing long-wave radiation

Figure 2: Examples showing monthly averages of wind speed (top), outgoing longwave radiation (mid), and the ocean mixed layer depth (bottom) over Europe in January 2020.

Example fields from both models showing some of the above mentioned variables are displayed in Fig. 2. Only the region of Europe is shown to better visualize the rich details of eddies in the ocean or regions of high and low wind speeds in mountainous areas.

The following section describes the access to the datasets via [WDCC](#).

4.3 Data access via WDCC

The *Cycle 2* datasets published in the context of this deliverable are findable and accessible via the [WDCC](#) search interface as follows:

Project:

[nextGEMS \(Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems\)](#)¹²

Experiment:

[nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS](#)¹³

Datasets

[ICON model output \(nextGEMS cycle 2\)](#)¹⁴

[IFS-FESOM model output \(nextGEMS cycle 2\)](#)¹⁵

Both datasets are reusable in compliance with CC-BY 4.0 license. The published Cycle 2 data are globally findable via a DOI assigned at the level of the *experiment*:

DOI:10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2 (Wieners et al., 2023)

In compliance with the [FAIR](#)¹⁶ principles, all metadata is openly accessible, while the data download is free for registered users. Interested users can register with [WDCC](#). Further, interoperability is achieved through the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data and file format standards. Reusability is achieved by supplying a standard license (CC-BY 4.0) and rich, domain-specific metadata.

Downloading the data is possible either via the [WDCC](#) graphical web interface or by using the command line tool [jblob](#)¹⁷.

¹²<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/project?acronym=nextGEMS>

¹³https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc2

¹⁴https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc2_ICON

¹⁵https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_cyc2_IFS

¹⁶<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=fairness>

¹⁷<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=jblob>

5 References (Bibliography)

References

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Wieners, Karl-Hermann; Ziemann, Florian Andreas; Koldunov, Nikolay; Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, Xabier; Rackow, Thomas; Redler, René; Sidorenko, Dmitry; Kölling, Tobias (2023). nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The nextGEMS *Cycle 2* data published and made available to the global scientific community in the framework of this deliverable are of very high general interest, since they represent the

first publicly available dataset covering one or two complete annual cycles simulated with state-of-the-art storm-resolving Earth-system models.

Publication of these data in [WDCC](#) facilitates uptake by all stakeholders because

1. [WDCC](#) supplied metadata is indexed in various searchable resources, e.g. Google Dataset Search
2. nextGEMS project reports will reference the data via their unique identifier and provide a citation
3. project-related communication and dissemination activities, e.g. on the project homepage, will include the data citation in the list of project outcomes
4. data reuse is very efficient due to the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data standards which enable allow low-barrier access and analysis of nextGEMS data

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26.06. - 02.07.2022 in Vienna
- mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04.04. - 06.04.2023

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>